

Deliverable 2.6

Summary report on student exchange

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Executive summary

By means of expert visits and staff exchanges GRINNAQUA will contribute to the elevation of the overall research profile of CIIMAR, increasing its profile and competitiveness at both the National and European levels, and at the same time supporting long-lasting collaborations between all participating partners. This document reports the students visits and their major outcomes. These took place during the first project period and have been already reported in Deliverable 4.3 – Summary reports of experts visits and staff exchange.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
BSL-3	Biosafety Level 3

1. Introduction

During the first 17 months of the project, the student exchanges in the context of GRINNAQUA were a great opportunity for CIIMAR PhD student to visit the partners' institutions and take advantage of the partners' team expertise. Between October 2022 and February 2023, CISA-INIA-CSIC received Inês Carvalho. In June 2023, three PhD students, Inês Ferreira, Inês Carvalho and Diogo Peixoto, visited the Roslin Institute / University of Edinburgh. This document describes the goals and outcomes of these exchanges.

2. PhD students' visits

2.1. CIIMAR PhD student visit to CSIC facilities

Main objective: Visiting laboratory and animal holding facilities with different security levels - the Widening Institute animal facility team will visit CSIC counterparts; Advanced training – students exchange.

Description: The PhD student Inês Carvalho visited Centro de Investigación en Sanidad Animal (CISA-INIA-CSIC), Madrid, Spain from October 2nd 2022 to February 2nd 2023. (Fig. 1)

Major outcomes: The visit provided a first-hand exposure to working in a Biosafety Level 3 (BSL-3) laboratory. The experience involved extensive training of the CIIMAR team member, on biosafety practices and procedures within a BSL-3 setting, covering the stringent security protocols, specialized containment measures for handling higher-risk pathogens and detailed decontamination processes.

Beyond the exposure to a high-level biological safety laboratory, techniques such as ELISPOT and flow cytometry were learned, expanding the skill set of the team at CIIMAR. Additionally, an in vitro trial was performed to assess the effects of methionine on immune- and antimicrobial-related genes using a rainbow trout intestine cell line.

Fig. 1: CIIMAR PhD student Inês Carvalho with Carolina Tafalla and Patricia Diaz-Rosales and their team during the visit to CISA-INIA-CSIC

2.2. CIIMAR PhD students visit to UEDIN facilities

Main objective: Advanced training – students exchange. Aiming at nurturing work relationships and collaboration between the project partners, and also at providing outside work experience and training with highly skilled researchers.

Description: Within the scope of the PhD student's thesis, Diogo Peixoto, Inês Carvalho and Inês Ferreira, several conducted trials resulted in transcriptomic (i.e., RNAseq) data, which had to be analysed. To achieve this, a stay at The Roslin Institute (UEDIN, Edinburgh, Scotland) from the 6th to the 16th of June of 2023 was essential. This stay was under the supervision of Dr Diego Robledo's and Dr Tim Bean's teams. (Fig. 2)

Major outcomes: The visit allowed the PhD students to improve their knowledge offering new insights into alignment and quantification pipelines (using Star), quantification using Kallisto, differential expression analysis, as well as R studio and Linux basic commands. Data visualization and interpretation skills acquired during this stay were also vital to further understanding the overall conclusion obtained in these trials. This stay was crucial for the analysis of this data and for equipping the PhD students with the advanced skills in transcriptomic analysis necessary for future studies.

Fig. 2: CIIMAR PhD students Inês Carvalho, Inês Ferreira and Diogo Peixoto with Roslin / UEDIN partners Diego Robledo and Tim Bean at the Roslin Institute

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